

FEATURES OF THE TEXT-FORMING FUNCTION OF SUBSTANTIVE COMPOSITES AND TEMPORAL CATEGORIES

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Abstract

The study of the temporal structure of text is associated with many problems, the impact of the text environment on semantics and the interdependence of substantive composites between functional-semantic speech types and corresponding temporal models are important. These aspects correspond to a certain extent to the principles of grammatical structure of text.

Keywords: Substantive composites, temporal category of text-forming function, functional-semantic types of speech, temporal dominant.

In German linguistics, substantive composites are one of the main layers of word formation, and all of its general and particular problems have been studied many times, but we consider it quite appropriate to return to this topic. The variety of theoretical and practical approaches to this problem in the temporal structure of the text expands and clarifies our data on the object of study, helps us in determining the universal principles of substantive composites of the studied language.

The method of studying substantive composites has been developed by representatives of the theory of content-oriented word formation. According to this method, groups of words with the same semantics are distinguished in the process of word formation - niches. Individual niches can be combined with niches with related semantics of different word formation types, thereby creating interdependent variants of a common concept, which find expression in different structures and form blocks. In H. Brinkmann's works, blocks of German nouns have been described in detail. The author analyzes such semantic-word formation groups as such as the block of general concepts (Gesamte Begriffe), diminutive words (Diminutiva), the concept of the subject (Subjektbegriffe), the names of tools (Werkzeugnamen), the concept of the process (Vorgangsbegriffe), etc. [2].

Among the extensive problems associated with the study of the temporal structure of text, important are the influence of the textual environment on the semantics and interdependence of substantive composites between functional-semantic speech types and corresponding temporal models. These aspects to a certain extent correspond to the principles of the grammatical structure of text. Substantive composites perform various functions in text. A derived word, distinguished by a certain lexical meaning, at the same time represents a structure with a derivational meaning, carries out a textual connection between words in terms of lexical semantics, on the one hand, and in terms of a more generalized meaning. On the other hand, various types of connections between derivatives (antonymic, synonymous, gradual) are actualized. Thus, the substantive composite performs the function of separation, gradation and expressiveness of the text. The text is a means of actualizing the mechanism of word formation from

various angles. The derived word finds its specific nature, its specific constructive character in the text. In the process of constructing a speech text, the effective nature of substantive composites is particularly clearly visible when creating a derived word. Substantive composites are a means of enhancing the expressiveness of the text, the actualization of its individual fragments, and the motivating factor of the linguistic sign at the level of "horizontal relations."

The study of the structural and content organization of the text, along with other problems, put the issue of temporal organization on the agenda. The text-forming function of the category of tense has already been discussed in the first studies on the linguistics of the text: the property of temporal integrity has been attributed to the text as an over-phrase unity, as well as to the text as an integral speech product. Data on the temporal structure of the text are still fragmentary, but are rapidly increasing, on one hand, in connection with new studies of the tense category, and on the other - in connection with the study of genre and functional-semantic speech types of the temporal structure of various types of text. It is also important that the category of tense is considered as a grammatical sign of the structural type of various functional-semantic types of speech.

Harald Weinrich's works are of particular importance in the study of the temporal structure of the text, as well as the tense forms used to form individual functional-semantic speech types in the modern German language. In his book „Tempus. Besprochene und erzählte Welt“ H. Weinrich distinguishes between two behavioral systems of the tense forms use in the German language and connects them with their concept of "reasoning on the world" and "narrative world". According to H. Weinrich, the subject of linguistics is two tense categories: paradigmatic - tense in the temporal system and syntagmatic - contextual tense together with other adjacent tenses. Tense in live speech, in a sentence and in a text can be presented to us in an infinite number of combinations with other forms of tense, but one of the tenses is given a clear advantage, especially in a complex sentence and in cases where the tense of the main sentence determines the tense of the subordinate sentence, which gave rise to the name *consecutio temporum*. H. Weinrich considers the tense forms of "reasoning on the world" - the tenses

Präsens, Perfekt, Futurum I and Futurum II (the so-called group I of temporal forms), tense forms of the "narrative world," respectively - Präteritum, Plusquamperfekt, Konditionalis I and Konditionalis II (group II of temporal forms), each group of tenses is inextricably linked to a certain language situation. [4, p. 36-45].

The study of the functioning of temporal localization devices in discourse allows us to determine their role in the creation of coherent discourse. Since in real communication the system of substantive composites does not interact directly with the text, but rather influences the consciousness that interprets or produces the text, we consider the system of substantive composites as an instruction for human mental activity. The purpose of the grammatical signals (morphemes, syntactic structures, composites) used to encode referenced connections in discourse is to activate specific mental operations in the listener's consciousness. These mental operations include two well-known cognitive aspects: a) activation of attention and b) search in memory (and hence selection). When studying linguistic material, the following regularities are noted: the emergence or even the appearance of substantive composites which results from the truncation of temporary forms. Moreover, the increased frequency of substantive composites in the text, in particular, in the journalistic text, pushes the temporal forms agreed with them to the background, they are truncated, and the given text becomes more graduated and expressive. With a relatively low frequency of substantive composites, the text becomes graduated and expressive by sharp changes in temporal forms, thus creating a polyphonic picture of the speech situation.

Considering such an interaction of substantive composites and their temporal forms against the background of such functional-semantic types of speech as reasoning, narration and description with appropriate variability, it can be argued that the increased frequency of substantive composites predetermines such a functional-semantic type of speech, such as description, because the description in terms of temporality is carried out by Präsens and the Perfekt in contact with it, which is clearly shown by the fragments from the book "Lehrgangsbegleitendes Skript. Skilehrer, Level 3».

An example from the book „Lehrgangsbegleitendes Skript. Skilehrer, Level 3“:

Auch bei der **Kurvensteuerung** spielen Kantbewegungen, Körperschwerpunkt- Verlagerungen und Drehbewegungen eine wichtige Rolle. *Kantbewegungen* erzeugen ein zunehmendes Aufkanten der Ski und damit steigendes Widerlager der Ski im Schnee. *KSP-Verlagerungen* erzeugen ein zunehmendes Einnehmen der Kurvenlage und eine stabilisierende Ausgleichsbewegung. *Drehbewegungen* lassen während der Kurvensteuerung die Ski in Verbindung mit einer KSP-Verlagerung zunehmend die Richtung ändern. Zusammenfassend findet idealerweise in der Kurvensteuerung ein weiteres Aufkanten der Ski, als auch Einnehmen der Kurvenlage mit zunehmender Ausgleichsbewegung statt. Dies geschieht in

Abhängigkeit von Tempo, Radius und Schneewiderstand [3].

An example from the book „Lehrgangsbegleitendes Skript. Skilehrer, Level 3“:

Durch die eigenständige Formulierung des Fahrgefühls oder einen positiven Einstieg des Skilehrers soll der Fahrer zum einen sensibilisiert und zum anderen offen für Korrekturvorschläge werden. Im Bereich der Kurzanalyse wird nicht mehr vom Hauptfehler, sondern vom Ist-Zustand gesprochen, da es beim Skifahren selten um Fehler geht, sondern meist um nicht angepasste Merkmale/Aktionen. Das nicht angepasste Merkmal wird klar und präzise angesprochen. Hierbei ist es wichtig, die Abweichung der jeweiligen Kurvenphase zuzuordnen und nicht den Bewegungsspielräumen. Die Korrekturmaßnahme soll z.B. in Form einer Bewegungs- oder Gefühlsaufgabe gegeben werden, die für den Fahrer schnell umsetzbar ist [3].

An example from the book „Lehrgangsbegleitendes Skript. Skilehrer, Level 3“:

Gerade in letzter Zeit ist der kinästhetische Analysator und seine Rezeptoren im Leistungs- und therapeutischen Training mit der „Entdeckung und Weiterentwicklung“ des propriozeptiven Trainings sehr stark in den Mittelpunkt gerückt. Im Skisport ist der kinästhetische Analysator wie in den meisten Sportarten entscheidend, da die Propriozeptoren die zentralen Fühler für die Lage- bzw. Positionsregulation auf dem Ski sind. Durch die reflektorische Rückkopplung mit dem Zentralnervensystem (ZNS) wird ständig versucht, sich an die vorherrschende Situation anzupassen. Durch diese permanente Regulation der Hauptbewegungen ist es möglich, die Bewegungsspielräume am Ski ideal auszunutzen [3, p. 3 - 19].

An example from a reader's letter of the newspaper "Berliner Morgenpost", 13.08.2000, „Guten Morgen“:

Zum Beispiel ich: Schnell vorm Ladenschluss geparkt, schnell noch lebenswichtige Vitamine gekauft, anschliessend zum Wagen gelaufen, vergessene Habseiligkeiten rausgeholt. Und nicht abgeschlossen, über Nacht! „Papperlapapp“. Na schön, nur soll dann auch griffbereit die Disigner-Sonnenbrille auf dem Beifahrersitz liegen, nebenbei noch 50 seltene CDs auf dem Rücksitz. Super! Und nix passiert [1].

The first example presents 15 substantive composites, 6 Präsens. The second example presents 12 substantive composites, 7 Präsens. The third example presents 10 substantive composites and 5 Präsens, and the fourth example presents 5 substantive composites, 1 Präsens, and 6 Perfekt. But all Perfekts are presented in a shortened form, with Partizip II. In addition to the fact that temporal forms are relegated to the background, Perfekt itself is also presented in a shortened form. This is due to the abundance of substantive composites.

The analysis of the temporal structure of the above-mentioned texts confirmed that the so-called "world of reasoning" prevails in them, since they are mainly understood in the temporal forms of the first group. The functional-semantic speech type that is mainly and more or less characteristic of the given texts should be recognized as a description, where the first sentence is a generalizer, which is introduced by the

rest. The following sentences implement, explain the first. They are in no way dependent on each other. Each of them can be omitted without harm to the entire text, changed, reduced or expanded at the expense of new details. If the linearity of the text is evident in the reasoning (chain, sequential nature of the reasoning), description. In the description, parallelism prevails, the subordination of individual elements. The description takes place, as we have already mentioned, in the Präsens and sometimes in the Perfekt in contact with it. Substantive composites are pushed into the background by the temporal forms agreed with them in the text, their shortening occurs, moreover, with the increased frequency of substantive composites, the Perfekt can be presented in an incomplete form with the incomplete form (without an auxiliary verb), as a result of the truncation of the temporal form which is caused, as we have already mentioned, precisely by the abundance of substantive composites.

The data obtained as a result of the study are of interest from the viewpoint of the relationship between

substantive composites, functional-semantic speech types and temporal models of the corresponding texts. Of course, it cannot be categorically stated that there is a strict and unambiguous connection, on the one hand, between substantive composites defined by the functional-semantic type of speech, on the other hand, between certain temporal forms, however, the relative determinacy of the temporal formation of functional-semantic types of speech in relation to substantive composites is beyond doubt.

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